

Numerical Computation of Closed Isobars

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Abstract

Closed isobars are cast as a one-parameter family of solutions to a set of nonlinear equations, formulated by dynamical systems theory. Numerical continuation in pressure generates an effective continuum, offering detailed probing of low pressure systems and tropical cyclones. Incorporating spectral techniques also enables the complete mapping of inflections in both latitude and longitude, with potential implications for pressure gradient and wind structure studies.

1 Introduction

Closed isobars, which frequently appear on standard weather charts [1], are periodic solutions of a dynamical system representing the spatial evolution of pressure contours [2]. In this study, pressure refers to ‘mean sea level pressure’ (MSLP), a fundamental quantity in atmospheric science and forecasting [3], generated by an atmospheric model on a regular latitude-longitude grid. Atmospheric low pressure systems and tropical cyclones are principal sources of closed isobars, which evolve in pressure to define a unique structure bounded by the so called ‘outermost closed isobar’ [4].

The initial task is to formulate the applicable dynamical system from gridded MSLP data, and numerically calculate periodic solutions [5] across a range of pressures, filling a spatial region with enough closed isobars to observe their detailed evolution in pressure. A range of numerical tools is employed, the first being interpolation, including first derivatives, as provided by the `scipy` library [6]. Solving the dynamical system to calculate isobars is achieved by the RK4 scheme [7], and closing the isobars requires NEWTON iteration [8] to solve a system of three nonlinear equations. Continuation in pressure subsequently allows ‘mass production’ of the closed isobars, filling the parameter space, and also the physical domain. Much of the computational methodology has previously been applied on a considerably larger dynamical

system, involving standing waves in free surface hydrodynamics [9]. Closed isobars can also be calculated by various software packages from the same data, however limitations in pressure increment, number of isobar points, and a requirement to precisely locate the opening/closing pressure have motivated the current study. For little extra effort, pressure derivatives are also available with every computed closed isobar, proving indispensable in further analysis.

Prior to calculating closed isobars, the applicable spatial sub-domain and associated pressure bounds must be established by locating Hopf points and saddle points [5], several of which may exist in the given data. The lowest pressure (Hopf, saddle) pair provides a storm track estimate [10, 11] and outermost closed isobar [4], the latter (homoclinic orbit) constructed by numerically solving the pressure equation. A FIGURE-8 structure emerges, comprising major and minor loops, the latter forming a weak secondary system for the data under consideration. Stationary points for both latitude and longitude, which mark the four extremities of the closed isobars, are also calculated across the pressure range, producing solution branches which serve as ‘axes’ dividing the domain into convenient ‘quadrants’.

The Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) assumes a key role in analysing the computed closed isobars, decomposing latitude and longitude into spectral components which evolve in pressure. Stationary points in the amplitude-pressure plane are located and presented as ‘feature isobars’, granted elevated status due to their strength (or weakness) of spectral content at a certain wavenumber. Such isobars occupy lines in the so called wavenumber-pressure plane, a rectangle onto which the original spatial domain is transformed, with ‘signatures’ appearing at specific wavenumbers. The DFT also proves itself as a valuable asset by supplying spectral differentiation [12], enabling extended calculations that also locate inflections on the isobars, yielding multiple solutions and accompanying turning points.

Turning an MSLP data set into thousands of closed isobars, on which applicable calculations are performed, may be viewed as just another way of spatially analysing such data, with various options available. Wavelet analysis, as applied to MSLP forecast errors [13], is also applicable to the MSLP field. On a much larger domain, spectral methods utilising spherical harmonics were applied to MSLP data on the entire southern hemisphere [14]. The suite of numerical tools for calculating and analysing closed isobars, as demonstrated in this study, is intended to offer meteorologists an additional capacity for probing the structure of tropical cyclones.

2 Numerical Isobar Calculation

2.1 Formulation

Isobars evolve on a sphere according to the dynamical system [2],

$$\dot{\theta} = -f_{\phi}(\theta, \phi), \dot{\phi} = f_{\theta}(\theta, \phi) \quad (1)$$

where $p = f(\theta, \phi)$ is the mean sea level pressure as a function of longitude θ and latitude ϕ , and subscripts denote partial derivatives. Numerical integration of (1) from any initial condition (θ_0, ϕ_0) with a suitably chosen step length produces an isobar segment approximation. Closed isobars, or periodic solutions [9, 5], satisfy a parametrised system of three nonlinear equations [5]

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{u}, p) = 0 \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{u} contains the (nonunique) initial condition (θ_0, ϕ_0) , and period T ,

$$\mathbf{u} = [\theta_0 \ \phi_0 \ T]^T.$$

The first two equations close the isobar, and the third enforces the pressure at the initial condition, $f(\theta_0, \phi_0) - p = 0$.

Any point (θ_0, ϕ_0) inside the low pressure system is actually an initial condition, what the solution to (2) also provides is the period T , or ‘lap time’, and the computed isobar points (θ_j, ϕ_j) . Standard numerical tools are applied to construct the system of equations (2), namely RK4 for the numerical integration[7], with $f(\theta, \phi)$ provided by a cubic spline interpolant [6], including derivatives, from grid data. Newton iteration [8] then produces the required solution at specified pressure, given a suitable starting guess. Subsequent continuation [15] in pressure p fills the parameter space, or required pressure range, effectively creating a continuum.

Before solving the system (2), stationary points of the dynamical system (1) are determined, also by Newton iteration [8], to establish the target pressure range and corresponding spatial domain. Hopf points, where periodic solutions are born [5], and saddle points, through which a homoclinic orbit passes, are both required by location and pressure. Multiple solutions are present in the data, the most relevant being those of lowest pressure. The Hopf point, or pressure minimum, serves as a storm track estimate [10, 11], while the saddle point lies on a FIGURE-8 isobar, the homoclinic orbit. Actually calculating the homoclinic orbit is achieved by solving $f(\theta, \phi) - p = 0$ for θ at given ϕ , and applying continuation in ϕ , or the same process with θ and ϕ interchanged. The resulting loops of the FIGURE-8, both of which contain closed isobars, identify as ‘major’ and ‘minor’, the latter forming a

weak secondary system. The former serves as the outermost closed isobar [4], bounding the focus region of study.

For the numerical integration of (1), period T is scaled out [5], so the calculation is performed on the interval $[0, 1]$ with $N = 2^n$ discrete intervals. In the interests of numerical convergence, several values of n are utilised, providing up to 1024 discrete isobar points. Once a converged solution to (2) is found, its derivatives with respect to pressure are immediately available by solving a linear system of equations [8]. Iterative methods require suitable initial guesses, requiring some initial experimentation for the period T , after which numerical continuation [15, 8] completes the task.

2.2 Mean Sea Level Pressure Data

Mean sea level pressure is a ubiquitous quantity in atmospheric science and forecasting [3]. The data for this study derives from an atmospheric model [16], and resides on a uniformly spaced grid with intervals $\Delta\theta = 0.83^\circ$ and $\Delta\phi = 0.55^\circ$, spanning a domain with longitude $\theta \in (167.5, 184.17)$ and latitude $\phi \in (-18.33, -35.0)$ degrees, during the tenure of TC WINSTON in February 2016 [17]. The actual data gridpoints have been included in the domain diagram of Figure 1. High resolution data of this type is available from a comprehensive archive covering the globe over numerous years at [18].

3 Numerical Results

3.1 Stationary Points

Multiple stationary points occur in the domain under consideration, the most important for this study being a Hopf point at $(175.72, -26.76)$, and its companion saddle point at $(176.04, -25.88)$, with pressures 999.74hPa and 1000.495hPa respectively. These two points, possessing the lowest pressure of their type, now define the subdomain of interest and applicable pressure range, as determined by the 1000.495hPa isobar passing through the saddle point. This homoclinic orbit, constructed by applying continuation [15] in longitude on the pressure equation $p = f(\theta, \phi)$, forms a FIGURE-8 structure in Figure 1, comprising a dominant primary system and weak secondary system containing a Hopf point at 1000.38hPa. In pressure terms, the primary system is 6.7 times stronger, while by size it is approximately 24 times larger in area and 5 times in perimeter. The primary loop serves as the outermost closed isobar [4] for subsequent calculations.

The other pertinent stationary points to be determined define coordinate

Figure 1: A selection of computed closed isobars with $n=8$, equally spaced in pressure, together with homoclinic orbit at 1000.495hPa, Hopf points and saddle point. Two additional ‘feature isobars’ represent local minima for average latitude and longitude, with branch curves for stationary points $\dot{\theta}=0$ and $\dot{\phi}=0$ also included. Actual gridpoints are marked with dots.

extremities for the closed isobars, or turning points where either $\dot{\theta}$ or $\dot{\phi}$ is zero. Respective solution branches included in Figure 1 intersect at the Hopf and saddle points, serving as a pair of ‘axes’ for the system of closed isobars, dividing the domain into ‘quadrants’ within which the signs of $\dot{\theta}$ and $\dot{\phi}$ remain unchanged. In axes terms, the east-west ($\dot{\theta}=0$) branch receives ‘major’ status, spanning 3.5° in longitude, amounting to 1.8 times the latitudinal span of the north-south ($\dot{\phi}=0$) branch.

Further compounding the latitude-longitude asymmetry is a large disparity in longitudinal displacement of the east and west extremities, the latter more than twice that of the former, resulting in egg shaped closed isobars. In addition, the west extremity migrates further south than its eastern counterpart, rotating the ‘major’ axis anti-clockwise. On the north-south ($\dot{\phi}=0$) branch, a smaller disparity arises in latitudinal displacement of the north

and south extremities, the latter 1.25 times that of the former. Western migration of the south extremity also sharply contrasts with the motion of the north extremity, which turns east at 1000.34hPa in order to pass through the saddle, after initially moving west.

No more than two stationary points for either coordinate have been detected at any pressure inside the primary system. Just outside, however, the picture changes dramatically due to a closed loop branch for $\dot{\theta}=0$ passing through the saddle and second Hopf point. This adds an extra pair of stationary points for longitude, necessitating an S-BEND manoeuvre in the isobars as they enclose the entire FIGURE-8 homoclinic orbit.

3.2 Closed Isobars and Pressure Derivatives

From an archive containing over 6700 closed isobars calculated with three different values of n (8,9 and 10), a small sample has been included in Figure 1, with pressure increment 0.1hPa, and $n=8$. Spanning 0.25° in longitude and 0.19° in latitude, the ‘innermost’ result at 999.76hPa is limited by the underlying interpolant and numerical methods, shrinking slightly as n increases. At the upper pressure boundary, the outermost result at 1000.493hPa(not shown) is almost indistinguishable from the homoclinic loop except in the saddle point vicinity.

As a first visual check, the calculated isobars in Figure 1 appear to closely conform with the included ‘axes’ that define their four extremities. The development of asymmetry with pressure can also be observed in the isobars, and pressure gradient activity is instantly visualised, displaying profound differences between quadrants. To complete the picture, a small sample of calculated closed isobars has also been included in the weak secondary system, with 0.02hPa spacing.

Two additional closed isobars appear in Figure 1 at 1000.16 and 1000.37hPa, included as the first examples of so called ‘feature isobars’, in this instance pertaining to the path traced by the isobars’ average coordinates, $(\bar{\theta}(p), \bar{\phi}(p))$, also plotted in the Figure. This curve spends most of its life in the south-west ‘quadrant’, reflecting the isobars’ asymmetry, turning through a local latitude minimum before entering the north-west ‘quadrant’. Soon after entry, the curve turns through a local longitude minimum, its second and final turn. These two turns become immediate targets to be located in pressure, a process facilitated by the relevant derivatives with respect to pressure, available at every discrete isobar point.

Derivatives with respect to pressure of the average coordinates, denoted by $(\bar{\theta}_p(p), \bar{\phi}_p(p))$, are simply the average of the derivatives $\left(\frac{\partial\theta_j}{\partial p}, \frac{\partial\phi_j}{\partial p}\right)$, and

Figure 2: Pressure derivatives of average latitude and longitude from Figure 1, both of which cross the horizontal axis once, calculated with $n=8$.

are displayed against pressure in Figure 2. Both derivatives are initially negative and continue decreasing until just after 1000hPa, subsequently turning within 0.05hPa of each other and approaching the horizontal axis. The first axis crossing, for $\bar{\phi}_p(p)$, occurs at 1000.16hPa, as determined by NEWTON/SECANT iteration, with $\bar{\theta}_p(p)$ following later at 1000.37hPa.

Having established the applicable pressure values, the associated ‘feature isobars’ are calculated and plotted in Figure 1, with enlarged markers indicating positive pressure derivatives for latitude ϕ at 1000.16hPa, and for longitude θ at 1000.37hPa. Only two sign changes occur in each case, dividing the isobars into distinct portions. Actual locations of the sign changes, also potential targets of interest, will naturally evolve with pressure, as will their total number at any pressure.

3.3 Accuracy and Numerical Convergence

With pressure enforced at the initial condition (θ_0, ϕ_0) only by the closed isobar equations (2), it is reasonable to check how the remaining calculated isobar points $(\theta_j, \phi_j), j > 1$ fare in this regard. Pressure error at any point on a calculated isobar is the difference between the interpolated value and the nominal isobar pressure, $f(\theta_j, \phi_j) - p$, as applied to the initial condition in the third equation of (2). Taking root mean square (RMS) values gives a representative error measure for each computed isobar, which has been (scatter) plotted against pressure for the available computed isobars at $n=8,9$ and 10 in Figure 3, the latter two comprising just over 2000 isobars each.

The ‘big-picture’ view of Figure 3 shows three clouds of points, one for each n , with a downward cloud movement as n increases demonstrating numerical convergence as expected. RMS error values remain well below one millionth of a percent across the pressure range, a testament to the RK4 method’s performance. Another aspect of note concerns ‘steepness’, which displays a similar pressure dependence for each cloud, comprising three distinct regimes. A short-lived initial steep climb gives way to a less intense climb at approximately 999.8hPa, with a final flattening taking place approximately halfway through the pressure range, noting the log vertical scale.

Looking closer at Figure 3, neighbouring clouds appear to overlap in certain pressure intervals, while remaining clearly separated in others. This is attributed to non-uniqueness of the initial condition, which directly translates to the RMS error, thus implying that some initial conditions are indeed better than others by this measure. Replacing the calculated initial condition (θ_0, ϕ_0) with an arbitrary calculated point (θ_j, ϕ_j) on the isobar will not immediately satisfy the equations (2), requiring some iterative correction to do so at the specified tolerance (10^{-12}). Actually implementing this process for every discrete point on the isobar at selected pressures provides a range estimate for the RMS error, marked as vertical lines. Overlap has indeed been detected at certain pressures, at which the worst case for $n=9$ lies above the best case for $n=8$.

4 Spectral Analysis – The Wavenumber Domain

Being periodic data, computed closed isobar points (θ_j, ϕ_j) are directly amenable to the discrete Fourier transform (DFT), widely employed for uncovering features not easily discernible in an original data domain [19]. Mean latitude and longitude are merely the zero wavenumber components in the wavenum-

Figure 3: RMS pressure error profiles against pressure for closed isobars calculated with $N=256$, 512 and 1024 intervals.

ber spectrum, which comprises amplitudes for 128 wavenumbers (modes) for $N=256$ discrete isobar points. The first non-zero wavenumber, or fundamental mode $k=1$, accounts for most of a closed isobar's size in terms of actual coordinate span. Associated with any wavenumber k is a wavelength, of potential relevance in the meteorology context, which increases with pressure according to the closed isobar's perimeter.

Spectral amplitude against pressure for the first three wavenumbers of latitude and longitude appear in Figure 4, offering a direct comparison between individual modes evolving in pressure. For the first two of these, longitude dominates across the entire pressure interval, reflecting the observed asymmetry in Figure 1. For the first wavenumber, longitude also distinguishes itself by possessing a local amplitude maximum, where its growth rate changes sign, just inside the high pressure boundary, at 1000.48hPa. This is the first of several stationary points in this Figure, located in pressure by NEWTON/SECANT iteration as for the zero wavenumber case, all qualifying as feature isobars.

Figure 4: Pressure evolution of the first three wavenumbers for longitude and latitude in the closed isobars of Figure 1, representing horizontal lines in the wavenumber-pressure plane views of Figures 5 and 6.

For the second wavenumber, longitude and latitude both undergo two stationary points comprising a local maximum followed by local minimum, the maxima closely spaced in pressure at 1000.19hPa and 1000.13hPa, the minima at 1000.3hPa and 1000.49hPa. In the third wavenumber, longitude loses its dominance at 1000.12hPa, subsequently regaining dominance at 1000.46hPa. The actual crossing pressures define another type of feature isobar, possessing equal contributions of a given wavenumber, with equal contributions from different wavenumbers also possible. After its pair of stationary points comprising local maximum at 1000.10hPa and local minimum at 1000.39hPa, the third wavenumber curve for longitude rises steeply and cuts the second wavenumber curve for latitude at 1000.48hPa. Latitude possesses just one stationary point at wavenumber 3, a local maximum at 1000.22hPa, during its brief interval of dominance.

4.1 The Wavenumber-Pressure Plane

Amplitude spectra for latitude and longitude evolve with pressure in the wavenumber-pressure plane, a portion of which, comprising the first 16 wavenumbers or one eighth of the spectrum, is displayed in Figure 5 for longitude θ . Amplitude is indicated in this Figure by background shading, with complementary contours [20] at selected levels to elucidate key behaviour. Growth rates $\frac{\partial a_k}{\partial p}$ also play a key role, changing sign at numerous stationary points included in the Figure as ‘signatures’ of associated feature isobars. Connecting these by zero growth rate contours [20] captures negative growth zones.

Low amplitude contours, starting at 10^{-5} , emanate from the wavenumber axis and move diagonally with decreasing steepness, cutting higher wavenumber lines as pressure increases, and diverging in the process. At sufficiently high amplitude, 0.1 in the Figure, contours start on the pressure axis and remain below the third wavenumber line. Intermediate amplitudes, above 0.002, undergo a more complex behaviour involving divergence and convergence as they encounter sign changes in growth rate, entering negative zones.

Wavenumbers 2 to 6 all cross a prominent closed loop structure formed by the zero growth rate contours, above 1000.1hPa, which contains most of the negative growth rates in the plane, occupying just under 10% by area [21]. The interior of this ‘primary’ loop contains five horizontal segments bounded by local amplitude maxima and minima in the respective wavenumbers. A secondary loop structure, of area just over one tenth that of the primary loop, closes on the upper pressure boundary, spanning wavenumbers 6 to 11 within a narrow pressure interval above 1000.45hPa. Wavenumber 6 cuts the secondary loop at a local amplitude maximum, its highest overall amplitude, and third stationary point. Wavenumber 7 cuts once with a local (and global) maximum at 1000.47hPa, its only stationary point, while wavenumbers 8 to 11 all make two cuts, local maxima followed by local minima. The last pair at wavenumber 11 are separated by only 0.02hPa. All stationary points have been determined by NEWTON/SECANT iteration as previously.

Wavenumber 8 is the first to encounter stationary activity at both ends of the pressure interval in Figure 5, with a closely spaced local maximum-minimum pair near the wavenumber axis. Additional pairs then appear at higher wavenumbers, creating a series of narrow ‘minor’ loop structures with near vertical orientation, confined below 999.85hPa.

Amplitude contours for latitude in Figure 6 have much in common with their longitude counterparts in Figure 5, rising diagonally and diverging before striking negative growth rate zones. Several such zones appear, the largest of which overlaps much of the primary loop for longitude, also included for comparison in the Figure. Overlap regions, representing simul-

Figure 5: Wavenumber-pressure plane representation for longitude θ , inside the major homoclinic loop of Figure 1. Background shading is spectral amplitude a_k , with zero contours of growth rate $\frac{\partial a_k}{\partial p}$ included, and calculated zeros marked by '+' signs.

taneous amplitude decline of certain components with pressure, will receive subsequent scrutiny as a key part of the wavenumber domain comparison between latitude and longitude.

While similar in area, the (primary) latitude loop is more complex due to its pattern of stationary points, four of which occur at wavenumber 5, compared with two for longitude at this wavenumber. Positive growth rates between the second and third of these, from 1000.36hPa(local amplitude minimum) to 1000.44hPa(local maximum), pull the bounding contour below the 5th wavenumber line in this interval, with similar behaviour after the fourth stationary point at 1000.477hPa. The latitude loop is effectively closed by the upper pressure boundary due to the absence of a second stationary point in the third wavenumber, for which negative growth rate persists after 1000.22hPa, with stationary points for neighbouring wavenumbers just inside this boundary.

The upper extremity of the primary latitude loop is actually just below the wavenumber 6 line, attracted by a near horizontal inflection, with small positive growth rate. In this close vicinity, intersecting boundary contours terminate the overlap region, which excludes the stationary point for longitude at 1000.23hPa, on the wavenumber 6 line. A similar phenomenon appears at wavenumber 9, in connection with a secondary overlap region situated near the upper pressure boundary, with zero growth rate contour turning just above the line. In this case the (near) inflection is reversed, with small negative growth rates, and the stationary point for longitude (local maximum) resides on the overlap region's (left) boundary. The right overlap boundary at wavenumber 9 is a close coincidence between stationary points for latitude and longitude, which agree in pressure to two decimal places, appearing indistinguishable in the Figure. For latitude, only two other wavenumbers are involved in this overlap, namely 8 and 10, contributing one stationary point each to the overlap boundary.

Figure 6: Wavenumber-pressure plane representation for latitude ϕ , inside the major homoclinic loop of Figure 1. Background shading is spectral amplitude, with selected contours, and zero contours of growth rate. Stationary points are marked by '+' symbols.

The secondary overlap region in Figure 6 actually involves the third largest negative growth rate zone for latitude, the second largest residing between wavenumbers 12 and 15, extending in pressure from 1000.19hPa at wavenumber 15 to 1000.41hPa at wavenumber 13. Some 25% larger, this structure fits the simple category seen earlier for longitude, with interior comprising four horizontal segments on which growth rate is negative, bounded by a local amplitude maximum on the left and local minimum on the right. In addition to being remote from the pressure boundaries, it is also remote from any negative growth rates in longitude, or free from overlap.

At the low pressure end, stationary activity is confined to the same portion of the plane as observed for longitude, again populated by multiple stationary points closely spaced in pressure. Overall, negative growth rates occupy a larger area than that of their longitude counterparts, but are still by far a minority in the plane.

The preceding analysis, limited to the first 16 wavenumbers, represents a first look in the wavenumber-pressure plane with an emphasis on stationary points and growth rate behaviour. Differences between latitude and longitude have clearly emerged in this view, and considerable scope exists for extension, starting with higher wavenumbers. The wavenumber-pressure plane is actually a slice of the 3D amplitude array which includes time as its third dimension, opening the possibility for additional views in the wavenumber-time and time-pressure planes. This also offers a potential means of comparison between storms at different locations and times.

4.2 Higher Derivatives and Inflections

On any computed closed isobar in Figure 1, both coordinates possess two stationary points to define their extremities, as marked by the included ‘axes’. In between two stationary points is at least one inflection, where first derivatives are stationary, and second derivatives are zero, giving at least two inflections on every closed isobar. Due to their implications on pressure gradients and wind structure, inflections are considered as exceptional points worthy of further numerical study. Spectral derivative approximations[12], which accurately reproduce first derivatives from the original isobar dynamics (1), also provide the required second derivatives for locating isobar inflections.

Completing the task involves locating zeros of second derivatives θ'' and ϕ'' , the spectrally calculated values of which are available at the computed isobar points $(\theta_j, \phi_j)_{j=0}^{N-1}$. Treating the index j as a continuous variable, cubic spline interpolation [6] is then employed in conjunction with NEWTON iteration [8] to locate the zeros in between neighbouring isobar points. This may be applied as a post-processing operation on calculated closed isobars, or al-

Figure 7: Calculated solution branches for inflection points, at which $\theta''=0$ or $\phi''=0$, from the closed isobar system in Figure 1. Isobars are shown at selected pressures where pairs of inflections are gained or lost, in Table (1). Reference curves for $\dot{\theta}=0$ and $\dot{\phi}=0$ are also included to display ‘quadrants’.

ternatively as a fourth equation appended to the system (2), with subsequent continuation in pressure [15] generating closed isobars and their inflections as by-products. Both approaches have contributed to the diagram in Figure 7, which returns to the original spatial domain of Figure 1, mapping the inflection structure of both coordinates. Previously defined ‘quadrants’ are also included for reference.

In Figure 7, the calculated inflection branches start close to their associated stationary points on the innermost available closed isobar, subsequently evolving as ‘principal’ branches across the full pressure interval. These two branches attract attention for their complex geometry, which includes a cusp-like feature in the south-east quadrant, and pronounced turning manoeuvres. The obligatory pair of inflections for any closed isobar, as initially provided by the principal branches, is soon joined by other pairs as pressure increases, with up to eight inflections occurring for each coordinate.

Table 1: Calculated singular points for the inflection branches in Figure 7, at which pairs of inflections are gained/lost.

Pressure hPa	Longitude θ	Latitude ϕ	Coordinate
1000.115	174.52	-27.08	ϕ
1000.261	175.72	-27.55	ϕ
1000.412	176.61	-27.33	ϕ
1000.157	176.16	-27.22	θ
1000.323	175.71	-26.12	θ
1000.416	174.49	-26.37	θ
1000.418	176.66	-27.22	θ

Pairs of inflections may be gained, or lost in one case for longitude, at certain pressures where solution branches undergo turns coinciding with zero eigenvalues of the associated Jacobian matrix [5, 8]. Determining these pressures by the method of [22] gives the results in Table (1), which represent another class of feature isobar, defined by a pressure and the location of a constituent point possessing particular properties. At these points both second and third derivatives are zero, indicating horizontal inflections in the respective *first* derivatives. The first of these occurs at 1000.11hPa for latitude, with longitude following soon after at 1000.15hPa. In the wavenumber-pressure plane, ‘signatures’ of these feature isobars are expected to be somewhat more complex than those of the previous variety, potentially involving multiple wavenumbers, and a topic for future investigation.

The key difference between latitude and longitude in the inflection branches of Figure 7 is the closed loop structure appearing for the latter, between 1000.15hPa and 1000.41hPa. During this interval θ gains three pairs of inflections, the last at 1000.416hPa, developing a total of eight inflections before losing a pair as the loop closes at 1000.418hPa. By contrast, latitude has only gained pairs of inflections, reaching a final total of eight.

A final noteworthy point of significance in Figure 7 is the lone intersection taking place between inflection branches for latitude and longitude, marking a point with simultaneous inflections in both coordinates. At calculated pressure of 1000.429hPa, and located at (174.41,-26.38), this concludes a chain of spatially localised events within a narrow pressure interval. The associated closed isobar, highly ranked among feature isobars for its rarity, is included in the Figure.

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5 Summary and Conclusions

Thousands of closed isobars have been calculated inside a weak low pressure system by numerically solving a set of three nonlinear equations representing periodic solutions, and applying continuation in pressure. As a valuable by-product, every computed closed isobar was accompanied by partial derivatives of its constituent points with respect to pressure, offering additional insights into pressure evolution behaviour.

Analysing the computed results began with an examination of pressure errors, which confirmed improvements as the number of discrete isobar points increased, subject to variations due to nonuniqueness of the initial condition. Spectral analysis transformed the spatial domain into a rectangular region, the wavenumber-pressure plane (k, hPa), allowing direct comparisons between latitude and longitude on the isobars. Limited to the first 16 wavenumbers, these comparisons clearly demonstrated a potential for further application on different datasets for cyclones and typhoons. Following individual spectral components in pressure, or constant wavenumber lines in the (k, hPa) plane, revealed stationary points which were located in pressure by NEWTON/SECANT iteration, defining a class of so called ‘feature isobars’.

The principal beneficiary of spectral techniques in this study was the targeting of inflection points in both latitude and longitude, deemed important for their connection to pressure gradients and wind structure. This was achieved by appending a fourth equation, enforcing a zero second derivative, to the original isobar equations, and once again applying continuation in pressure. With up to eight solutions appearing on an isobar, the focus turned to transition points at which pairs of inflections were gained/lost, also located in pressure to introduce another class of feature isobars. A full spatial map of the inflection structure transpired, including an isobar with inflections in both coordinates at the same location.

The numerical toolset developed and tested on a weak low pressure system stands ready for further application on tropical cyclones and typhoons, offering meteorologists an additional probing device. Multiple storms will be

analysed and compared via their closed isobar structure, including temporal evolution, with the aid of spectral tools. A useful preliminary exercise is to repeat the previous calculations on data from the archive [18] at the same time and location, with different resolution and model.

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